

**Should the Government of Nigeria impose a
permanent ban on oil exploration in Niger Delta in
Southern Nigeria?**

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Abstract

Despite the global shift towards cleaner energy sources, Nigeria still relies heavily on oil exports as its primary source of foreign revenue (*Nigeria - Market Overview, 2023*). Almost 70 years ago, Nigeria discovered an abundance of oil and natural gas in the Niger Delta region of the country. However, the exploration and production of oil in this region has had devastating effects on the environment and the local community's health.

This paper is an individual project for the Sustainability and Leadership course under the teaching of Professor Rae Andre and Dr Alex Mifsud. As a personal project, I am focusing on the impact of oil spillage and pollution in Niger Delta and posing the question of whether the Nigerian government (my client) should allow oil corporations to continue oil exploration in the Niger Delta region considering its detrimental impacts to the community whose primary source of livelihood is fish farming.

This paper will weigh the pros and cons of oil exploration to the Niger Delta community, the Nigerian government, and oil and gas industry leaders. It will also analyze the scientific findings regarding oil pollution and the consequences of climate change. Based on these findings, the paper recommends that the Nigerian government should discontinue oil exploration in the Niger Delta region and take immediate steps to implement the recommendations of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) in 2011 after an extensive scientific investigation of the effects of oil pollution in Niger Delta (UNEP, 2011).

1.0 The Problem

The Niger Delta, a southern area in Nigeria, is one of the most vital wetlands and coastal marine ecosystems globally. The region currently faces severe environmental degradation due to decades of oil exploration. In 2011, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) published a 262-page report on its assessment of the oil pollution in Ogoniland, one of the local communities in the Niger Delta. Interestingly, the report was conducted at the behest of the Nigerian federal government to understand the nature and extent of oil contamination in Ogoniland (UNEP, 2011). The report identified severe environmental damage affecting land, groundwater, surface water, vegetation, and air quality, emphasizing the urgent need for intervention. Interestingly, there were critical scientific findings that pervasive oil contamination across various

environmental components persists in Ogoniland despite the cessation of oil extraction activities since 1993 (UNEP, 2011).

The environmental consequences of oil exploration directly violate the fundamental human rights of the Niger Delta communities. The pollution has degraded the available water quality, often leaving residents to rely on contaminated sources for drinking, cooking, and other domestic uses. This situation has heightened health risks and led to a widespread economic decline as the communities' means of livelihood are continuously undermined (Amnesty International, 2009/2009).

Today, communities like Ogale and Bille in Niger Delta are instituting lawsuits in the UK against the giant oil corporation Shell since climate litigation remains a relatively unfamiliar concept in Nigeria, prompting victims to seek justice in jurisdictions where the parent companies of these major oil firms are based (Amnesty International, 2021). Fortunately, in 2021, a Dutch court ruled that Shell was responsible for damages caused by oil spills in several Niger Delta villages, mandating compensation and stricter preventive measures for future incidents (*Shell in Nigeria - Olievervuiling En Armoede in De Nigerdelta*, 2023).

The question is, will the Nigerian government put a permanent ban on oil exploration in the Niger Delta? The country is largely dependent on the foreign revenue it generates from the exportation of crude oil. A discontinuation of oil exploration would not only hurt the Nigerian economy but would also hurt Nigerians, especially the people from Niger Delta. The Nigerian 1999 Constitution and the Revenue Allocation Act allocates a certain percentage of oil revenues to the states from which they are generated. Historically, this has been set at 13%, and the remaining balance is then shared amongst the federal, state, and local governments (*Revenue Allocation / NEITI*, n.d.). A permanent ban on oil exploration would mean that Niger Delta states would no longer access its exclusive 13% oil revenue though it did not seem to have made their lives better. A decision to place a permanent ban without a sustainable alternative to protect the interests of stakeholders will be met with stiff opposition.

A limitation of this research and its recommendation is that it is focused on specific parts of Niger Delta that has been the subject of peer reviewed papers and International Organizations' investigations as I do not have the time nor resource to conduct fresh investigation in areas not mentioned in these reports.

2.0 The Stakeholders

2.1 *Local Communities*

Undoubtedly, the local communities in the Niger Delta are the most significant stakeholders, as the discovery of oil in their villages caused a huge decline in their traditional way of life. The UNEP report documented the extent of hydrocarbon pollution in Ogoniland, with contamination levels far exceeding the safe thresholds set by Nigerian environmental regulations (UNEP, 2011). Hydrocarbons in soil and water, particularly carcinogenic compounds like PAHs, pose significant health risks to the community (Umar et al., 2023).

Remarkably, the residents of the Niger Delta have not sat back to watch the depletion of their communities. In 1995, the famous Ogoni Nine were unjustly executed for their opposition to the government and Shell's exploitation of their community (*Één Nigeriaanse Weduwe Vs Shell - Amnesty International*, 2022). Almost 29 years later, a lawsuit instituted by one of the widows of the Ogoni Nine in the Netherlands was heard and dismissed by the Hague for insufficient evidence to hold Shell liable for the deaths of the Ogoni Nine (Ibid). Another set of residents were successfully heard in the Netherlands in 2021 after almost 15 years of litigation, and the court awarded monetary compensation and stricter preventive measures for future incidents (*Shell in Nigeria - Olievervuiling En Armoede in De Nigerdelta*, 2023).

2.2 *International Organizations*

For years, International Organizations like Amnesty International and United Nations have fought for the rights of the inhabitants of the Niger Delta region. The UNEP's extensive report shows how far the international organization would go to research, document, and make recommendations to improve the wellbeing of local communities.

Amnesty has been critical of the role of international oil companies in the Niger Delta, such as Shell and has repeatedly called for them to take responsibility for oil spills, reduce further environmental damage, and commit to transparent operations. It also criticized the actions of the Nigerian government in the execution of the Ogoni Nine and the failure of the government to protect its citizens and guarantee their fundamental human rights.

Through its various bodies, the UN advocates for stronger environmental governance, the enforcement of existing laws, and the creation of new policies that better protect the environment and the rights of affected communities. It also pushes for greater corporate responsibility and accountability from oil companies operating in the region. As stakeholders, international organizations act as watchdogs in monitoring how the national government enforces their citizens' human rights. Without these stakeholders, the victims might not have advocates for violation of their rights.

2.3 *Nigerian government*

In Nigeria, companies engaged in upstream petroleum operations are subject to taxation under the Petroleum Profits Tax Act, which subjects such companies to multiple tax rates that range from 30% to 85% on various levels of profits from different operations (*Nigeria - Corporate - Taxes on Corporate Income*, n.d.) compared to the 30% company income flat tax rate for other types of companies. Additionally, the new Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) introduced more taxes on the oil and gas sector. The Nigerian government generates massive revenue from the oil and gas sector annually, with foreign exchange revenue generated constituting almost 90% of the country's foreign earnings (*Nigeria - Market Overview*, 2023).

The government has indicated on several instances its willingness to address the ongoing pollution in Niger Delta, however, nothing substantive has been done. Based on UNEP's recommendations, the government set up a cleanup project, managed by the Hydrocarbon Pollution Remediation Project (HYPREP), to remediate oil-contaminated sites in Ogoniland and restore affected communities. However, Amnesty International's investigation in 2021 detailed that only 11% of the polluted sites have seen the beginning of cleanup activities due to conflicts of interest within the management of HYPREP (Amnesty International, 2021).

Through the PIA enacted in 2021, the government introduced stricter regulatory and compliance measures to mitigate environmental damage and encourage sustainable practices within the industry. However, a contentious aspect of the Act is its imposition of responsibilities on host communities for protecting oil and gas infrastructure. Communities that fail to prevent

vandalism of oil assets are held liable for repair costs (Nwuke, 2021). This provision makes it clear where the interests of the Nigerian government lie.

2.4 *Oil and Gas Industry Leaders*

Oil and gas industry leaders are critical stakeholders in addressing oil pollution in the Niger Delta due to their direct involvement in the exploration, extraction, and processing of petroleum resources. A peer-reviewed paper (Herzog-Hawelka & Gupta, 2023) found that 100 fossil fuel companies account for 70% of the greenhouse gas emissions over the past 30 years. The primary contributors are four investor-owned oil and gas corporations: ExxonMobil, Chevron, BP, and Shell (Herzog-Hawelka & Gupta, 2023). This shows the impact of oil and gas leaders in climate change and its consequent impacts on residents in areas where oil and gas are being exploited.

For oil and gas companies operating in Nigeria, a permanent ban on oil exploration in Niger Delta is an end to the revenue they generate from the country. Nigeria has been a substantial part of Shell's oil production portfolio, and this is further indicated in the Company's plan to sell its onshore oil business in Nigeria for \$1.3bn even though it will maintain its deep-water oil, natural gas, and solar energy businesses in Nigeria, after the sale (Hurst, 2024).

3.0 Science

Oil and gas companies are significant contributors to global greenhouse gas emissions. Research shows that the combustion of fossil fuels by these industries releases over 30,000 Mt of CO₂ annually, making them one of the largest sources of GHG emissions worldwide (Herzog-Hawelka & Gupta, 2023). The Niger Delta has suffered extensive environmental degradation due to relentless oil extraction practices, which has not only aggravated the global climate crisis but has also severely impacted local ecosystems and biodiversity.

To truly understand the plight of the local communities in Niger Delta and the extent of oil pollution in their communities, I will present findings from peer reviewed papers on how oil contamination in Niger Delta is detrimental not only to the health of the people but also its economy.

3.1 Health Impacts of soil and groundwater contamination

Fish farming is the primary source of livelihood for the people of the Niger Delta. UNEP's report found that hydrocarbon pollution has extensively contaminated critical resources in Niger Delta. A recent peer-reviewed paper (Umar et al., 2023) further confirmed UNEP's findings when the researchers analyzed soil samples for benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene (BTEX), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH), total oil and grease (TOG), and total organic carbon (TOC) using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for mapping oil spill hotspots and employed the resistivity method to delineate hydrocarbon pollution to depths of up to 19.7 meters.

Image source: <https://www.amnesty.nl/content/uploads/2017/01/HH-12368059.jpg?x97109=undefined&ixlib=imgixjs-3.5.1&w=1946>

Umar et al. (2023) found that the presence of hydrocarbons in soil and water, particularly carcinogenic compounds like PAHs, poses significant health risks to the community. Exposure to these pollutants can lead to long-term health issues, including cancer and other serious illnesses.

3.2 Ecological impacts on aquatic and vegetative life

PAHs are identified as among the most toxic components of crude oil, which are particularly harmful due to their ability to dissolve in water and thus be readily absorbed by marine life. PAHs are linked to a range of detrimental effects, including immune system modulation, neurotoxicity, and reproductive issues (Ruberg et al., 2021). Marine turtles risk inhaling toxic PAHs when they surface for air within oil slicks, leading to acute mortality and long-term health issues (Ruberg et al., 2021). Another peer-reviewed article also noted that the toxicity effects of hydrocarbons and PAH compounds can lead to acute mortality and chronic reproductive and developmental issues in marine life (Liu et al., 2022).

For communities in the Niger Delta, where fish farming and agriculture are primary sources of livelihood, the UNEP report has highlighted the grave extent of this pollution, estimating that it could take 25 to 30 years to fully clean up the environmental damage caused by more than five decades of oil operations (UNEP, 2011).

3.3 Health implications on residents in Niger Delta

One article (Ordinioha & Brisibe, 2013) estimated that, on average, 240,000 barrels of crude oil are spilled annually in the Niger Delta due to various causes, and the contamination from spills can lead to severe health issues, including a 60% reduction in household food security and notable increases in the prevalence of childhood malnutrition by 24%. Toxic elements like polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and heavy metals found in the environment can cause diseases such as cancer and impair developmental and reproductive functions (ibid).

As George et al. (2023) found, the transportation of petroleum products has resulted in heavy metal deposits in the environment, which has severe implications for aquatic life and human health as these metals accumulate in the food chain. Researchers have discovered that in Nigeria, infants are twice as likely to pass away within their first month of life if their mothers resided near an oil spill prior to becoming pregnant (Hodal, 2022). All these point to the health implications for residents in Niger Delta.

I searched Northeastern library and Google Scholar databases using the keywords “hydrocarbon pollution” and “benefits,” and examined five articles. However, I found no refuting evidence that oil pollutants do not affect people's health and well-being.

4.0 Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, I propose that Nigeria should place a permanent ban on oil exploration in Niger Delta. It is high time that Nigeria looked beyond the immediate profits from the oil and gas sector and considered the plight of its citizens by upholding their fundamental rights. One effective way is to place a permanent ban on oil exploration in Niger Delta. It should also take immediate action to fully implement UNEP's recommendations instead of building additional refineries. As Amnesty International reported, "It is clear that the government of Nigeria is failing in its duty to control the oil industry and prevent environmental damage and human rights abuses" (Amnesty International, 2013).

One of the arguments against this recommendation is the impact of the ban on Nigeria's revenue source. However, while oil production contributes significantly to Nigeria's foreign earnings, it contributes only 5.6% of its GDP (Statista, 2023). Unfortunately, even with the derivation principle entrenched in the constitution, the local communities of the Niger Delta see little to no benefit from the massive revenue of \$600bn that is estimated to have been earned since oil explorations began over 50 years ago (Amnesty International, 2009). Instead, they experience economic displacement as fishing and farming become untenable due to environmental contamination.

Banning oil exploration in the Niger Delta could encourage the development of alternative, sustainable economic activities. Investing in renewable energy, agriculture, and tourism would diversify the economy, reduce dependency on oil, and promote long-term sustainable development in the country.

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